

CONDITION OF SPARINGLY SOLUBLE SALTS OF LEAD AND ZINC IN GELATIN

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The condition of the sparingly soluble salts of lead and zinc in gelatin sol has been studied. E.M.F. of these salts in gelatin at various concentrations was measured and percentage of the cation of respective salts calculated. The low percentage definitely indicates that the sparingly soluble substances are not in ionic condition, as is required for supersaturation, but are in the colloidal state.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 529) it has been shown that almost all the sparingly soluble salts of copper and silver in gelatin are in the colloidal state. The study has been extended to salts of lead and zinc in gelatin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lead nitrate (AnalaR) from B. D. H. was used in the preparation of the solutions, while in case of zinc a stock solution of zinc chloride was prepared by dissolving AnalaR zinc in hydrochloric acid (A. R.). The mixture was warmed gently until no further zinc dissolved. The solution was filtered and shaken with zinc hydroxide and kept for several days. The concentration was determined by estimating both zinc and chloride. They gave concurrent results. The results are :—

Zinc ammonium phosphate in 10 c.c. of the solution = 0.1770 g., 0.1772 g.

Silver chloride in 10 c.c. of the solution = 0.2862 g., 0.2860 g.

Normality of the soln. calculated from phosphate = 0.1985.

Normality of the soln. calculated from chloride = 0.1990

Electrodes of lead and zinc were slightly amalgamated in order to prevent oxidation. Getman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 40, 6) showed definitely that the E. M. F. obtained with different specimens of lead cast sticks with electrolytically deposited lead and with amalgam were practically identical. The electrode vessel used was of the type used by Getman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2655) and hydrogen was used to keep the solution and atmosphere in the electrode vessel free from oxygen.

The other experimental work was carried out on the same lines as of Chatterji and Dhar (this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 177). The same preparation of gelatin was used throughout the experiments. The sparingly soluble salt was prepared by adding the salt solution of the respective metal to the

gelatin solution, then adding dropwise slowly with stirring the precipitating salt solution. The results are given below. The cell used was as follows:—

5% Gelatin was used in each experiment (where M is Pb or Zn).

TABLE I

No.	E.M.F.	Conc. of the salt.	Conc. of Pb present as ions.	%Pb as ions.
With lead ferrocyanide.				
1	0.08754	1000N × 10 ⁶	2.926 N × 10 ⁴	0.2926
2	0.08660	500	3.135	0.5270
3	0.08787	250	2.847	1.0384
4	0.09067	120	2.245	1.7960
With lead oxalate.				
1	0.10490	1000N × 10 ⁶	0.736N × 10 ⁴	0.0736
2	0.10260	500	0.886	0.1766
3	0.09776	250	0.298	0.5192
4	0.09370	125	1.740	1.4360
With lead phosphate.				
1	0.10740	1000N × 10 ⁶	0.630N × 10 ⁵	0.0603
2	0.09857	500	1.220	0.2440
3	0.09524	250	1.645	0.6580
4	0.09263	125	1.951	1.5608
With lead arsenate.				
1	0.09848	1000 N × 10 ⁶	1.226 N × 10 ⁴	0.1226
2	0.09564	500	1.535	0.3070
3	0.09172	250	2.090	0.8360
4	0.08879	125	2.650	2.1200
With lead iodide.				
1	0.04550	100 N × 10 ⁴	8.210 N × 10 ⁴	8.2100
2	0.05211	50	4.867	9.7340
3	0.06179	25	2.245	8.9800
4	0.07283	12.5	0.940	7.5200

TABLE II

No.	E.M.F.	Conc. of the salt.	Conc. of Pb present as ions.	%Pb as ions.
With zinc oxalate				
1	0.11900	10000 N × 10 ⁶	2.721 N × 10 ⁶	0.02721
2	0.1325	5000	10.066	0.20130
3	0.09460	2500	18.870	0.75480
4	0.08857	1250	30.435	2.43580
With zinc chromate.				
1	0.11200	10000N × 10 ⁶	4.664N × 10 ⁴	0.04664
2	0.09124	5000	24.590	0.49180
3	0.08214	2500	50.650	2.02600
With zinc selenite.				
1	0.09620	1000 N × 10 ⁶	1.6475 N × 10 ⁵	0.16475
2	0.07370	500	9.4050	1.83100
3	0.09020	250	3.1460	1.25840

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing results it is observed that in cases of lead ferrocyanide, lead oxalate, lead phosphate and lead arsenate and of zinc oxalate, chromate and selenite, the percentage of respective cation, which is in ionic condition, is small, whereas in case of lead iodide, it is found that the lead in ionic condition is more than that found in the other group. It may be observed that in this sparingly soluble salt the solubility of which is comparatively large, it has been found that the ionic condition of such salt is increased, whereas in case of salts which have low solubility, the percentage present in the ionic condition in gel is small. This suggests that there is some relation between the solubility and the power to form the supersaturated solutions. This is being studied in detail in this laboratory.

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